

Evaluation of the Accuracy of MRI in Painful Shoulder with Arthroscopic/Surgical Correlation**Sidharth Goel¹, (Col). Kamal K. Sen², Sudhansu Sekhar Mohanty³, Basanta Manjari Swain⁴, Sangram Panda⁵, Devesh Vijay Bobde⁶**¹Post Graduate Resident (3rd year), Department of Radiodiagnosis, Kalinga Institute of Medical Sciences, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India²Professor, Department of Radiodiagnosis, Kalinga Institute of Medical Sciences, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India³Associate Professor, Department of Radiodiagnosis, Kalinga Institute of Medical Sciences, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India⁴Professor & Head, Department of Radiodiagnosis, Kalinga Institute of Medical Sciences, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India⁵Associate Professor, Department of Radiodiagnosis, Kalinga Institute of Medical Sciences, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India⁶Post Graduate Resident (3rd year), Department of Radiodiagnosis, Kalinga Institute of Medical Sciences, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Objectives:** The present study was to find the diagnostic accuracy of MRI in characterizing the causes of shoulder pain in correlation with arthroscopy/surgery. And it was also to evaluate the detection and characterization of the underlying shoulder pathology in the cases of shoulder pain.**Methods:** MRI protocol consists of positioning the patient in supine position with external rotation of the arm. Adequate support for head and the limb is provided. Dedicated surface coil (Helmholtz pair) for shoulder is used. Technique for MRI of shoulder: After obtaining localizer in all three orthogonal planes, following sequences are obtained: Axial STIR & PD FATSAT Coronal T1, GRE and T2 FATSAT Sagittal T2 FATSAT.**Results:** All the 52 participants were first assessed first by MRI scan followed by arthroscopy. The MRI scans reported 20 (38.5%) FTT and 29 (55.8%) PTT. On the other hand, arthroscopy revealed 24 (46.2%) FTT and 25 (48.1%) partial thickness tears (PTT). Three (5.8%) participants did not have any grades of tears as per both the investigations. Forty-four (84.6%) of the 52 participants in our study had the same diagnosis with arthroscopy and MRI. Only 8 (15.4%) participants had different arthroscopy findings than their MRI scans. As per MRI scans and arthroscopy, there were 15 (28.8%) and 18 (34.6%) Bankart lesions, respectively. there were 14 (26.9%) and 13 (25.0%) Hill-Sach lesions, respectively. 35(67%) cases showed joint effusion on MRI and 37(71%) showed effusion. Bursitis was seen in 20 out of 52 cases on MRI and 17 on arthroscopy. 3 were diagnosed to have impingement on MRI which was confirmed on arthroscopy.**Conclusions:** MRI showed excellent diagnostic accuracy in evaluation of impingement syndrome, joint effusion and bursitis in correlation with arthroscopy. Hence, MRI serves as a valuable non-invasive tool for guiding clinical decision-making and optimizing outcomes in patients of shoulder pain.**Key words:** Shoulder pain, MRI, Arthroscopy.

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Introduction

A shoulder discomfort episode occurs annually in close to fifty percent of the population [1,2]. Patients of all ages are affected by shoulder issues. Stress from the job has been traced to shoulder pain at work [1,3]. The shoulder's soft tissues and joints can cause pain in the shoulder or in the area around it. Acromioclavicular, sternoclavicular, and glenohumeral joints are the important joints around the shoulder [4]. The scapulothoracic plane and the

sub acromial bursa are examples of motion planes and bursa. Pain is the most frequent cause of seeking medical attention, regardless of the ailment. Pain and severe mobility restriction are common with adhesive capsulitis, also known as frozen shoulder [5,6].

The most commonly utilized imaging modality for diseases of the shoulder is conventional radiography [7]. Diagnostic imaging and potential

surgical procedures depend on imaging, physical examinations, clinical histories, and arthroscopy. Certain imaging modalities, including as magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), as well as ultrasound (US), are frequently employed [7]. Magnetic resonance arthrography (MRA) has been the preferred method for diagnosing shoulder injuries over MRI in the past couple of decades [7,8]. The preferred imaging test for assessing shoulder joint disorders is MRI due to its excellent soft tissue contrast plus spatial resolution [9]. The glenoid labrum and its attachments, the restraining rotator cuff muscles, and soft tissue structural lesions affecting the joint capsule can all be evaluated by MRI, which also includes MRA. When designing a patient's treatment plan, imaging modalities such as MRIs must be taken into account [8,9].

The stability of the glenohumeral joint comes from an intricate balance between dynamic stabilizers, such as the rotator cuff muscles, and static stabilizers, such as the glenohumeral joint labroligamentous complex, joint capsule, and osseous structures [10]. A wide range of motion is necessary for proper shoulder function without sacrificing stability, which requires careful coordination between shoulder mobilizers and stabilizers. Pain alleviation combined with a recovery of shoulder durability and range of movement are the objectives of rotator cuff therapy. Initially, conservative measures may be taken to treat rotator cuff injuries [11,10].

The prognosis and choice of treatment can be affected by information obtained from MRI regarding rotator cuff tears, including tear size, thickness or depth, tendon retraction, and shape. Furthermore, the rotator cuff's physiologic and mechanical state are affected by tear extension to neighbouring tissues, muscular atrophy, cross-sectional area enlargement, and fatty degeneration [8,9]. Nowadays, there are numerous of choices available for the investigations. Among these, MRIs and arthroscopies are the two most often employed procedures globally [12,13]. Objectives of our study was to find the diagnostic accuracy of MRI in characterizing the causes of shoulder pain in correlation with arthroscopy/surgery. And it was also to evaluate the detection and characterization of the underlying shoulder pathology in the cases of shoulder pain.

Material & Methods

This prospective, observational, hospital-based study was planned to evaluate the accuracy of magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) in the painful shoulder conditions and to correlate with the arthroscopic findings. This study was carried out in

the Department of Radiodiagnosis, Kalinga Institute of Medical Sciences, Bhubaneswar from 5th July 2022 to 19th May 2024. For this study, we got ethical approval (letter no. KIIT/KIMS/IEC/979/2022 dated 20/06/2022) from Institutional Ethics Committee, Kalinga Institute of Medical Sciences, Bhubaneswar, before we started the study (Annexure I). Written informed consent (Annexure II) was obtained from all the study participants prior to their enrolment.

Study population:

Adult individuals with suspected rotator cuff tear, who visited the Orthopaedics OPD, Kalinga Institute of Medical Sciences, Bhubaneswar, during the stipulated time period, were screened for their eligibility for this study. The convenience sampling method was applied for this study. The inclusion and exclusion criteria of the study were as follows:

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Adult patients aged of either sex between 18 and 65 years.
2. Patients with shoulder pain who have undergone both MRI shoulder followed by arthroscopy/surgery.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Patient with age less than 18 years or more than 65 years.
2. Patients who will not undergo either of MRI or arthroscopy /surgery.
3. Patients in whom MRI is contraindicated. (like pacemakers, ferromagnetic metallic implants, intraocular foreign bodies etc.)

Data Acquisition:

After clinical evaluation, once a patient satisfied the inclusion and exclusion criteria for this study, he or she would undergo the MRI evaluation after giving consent. All the MRI scans in this study were performed using 1.5 T MRI scanner (Signa HDxt; GE Medical systems)

MRI Protocol:

MRI protocol consists of positioning the patient in supine position with external rotation of the arm. Adequate support for head and the limb is provided. Dedicated surface coil (Helmholtz pair) for shoulder is used.

Technique for MRI of shoulder: After obtaining localizer in all three orthogonal planes, following sequences are obtained: Axial STIR & PD FATSAT Coronal T1, GRE and T2 FATSAT Sagittal T2 FATSAT.

Table 1: following parameters were used during acquisition of images.

	T1W	T2- FATSAT	GRE	STIR	PD-FATSAT
TR	400	3400	350	4900	2880
TE	10	63	13	20	40
Matrix	256x160	256x224	384x192	320x192	256x224
No of excitations	2	3	2	2	3
Thickness mm	4	4	4	3	3
Section spacing mm	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.5	1.5
FOV	18	16	18	17	17
Imaging time min	2min14sec	2min40sec	2min12sec	4min20sec	3min15sec

Table 2: MRI Sequences with pathological importance

MRI Sequence	Pathological Importance
T1-weighted	Provides excellent anatomical detail, useful for assessing bone morphology, presence of fractures, and joint spaces.
T2-weighted	Highlights fluid-filled structures (e.g., joint effusion, cysts), edema, and soft tissue abnormalities (e.g., tears).
PD (Proton Density)	Good for evaluating soft tissue structures and fluid without fat suppression, helpful for assessing ligaments and tendons.
STIR (Short Tau Inversion Recovery)	Suppresses fat signal, enhances contrast between fluid and surrounding tissues, useful for detecting edema and inflammation.
Gradient Echo (GRE)	Useful for assessing cartilage, detecting hemorrhage, and evaluating vascularity.
Fat-Suppressed T2-weighted	Suppresses fat signal, enhances visualization of fluid-filled structures, useful for detecting tears and lesions.

These above sequences were used in combination to provide a comprehensive assessment of shoulder pathology, including rotator cuff tears, labral tears, ligament injuries, bursitis, arthritis, and other conditions affecting the shoulder joint.

Statistical Analysis

Data was analysed by using R-Software (version 4.2.3). Mean \pm Standard deviations were observed. P-value was taken less than or equal to 0.05 ($p \leq 0.05$) for significant differences.

Observations & Results

Total 52 cases of painful shoulder fulfilling the inclusion and exclusion criteria of the study were included. The observations of these 52 patients were compiled and analysed.

The majority of the study participants were aged between 45-50 years (10), followed by 40-45 years (9), 50-55 years (8), 60-65 years (8), 35-40 years (7), 30-35 years (4), 65-70 years (4), and 55-60

years (2). The mean age of the study population at the baseline visit was 49.5 ± 13.9 years. The age range was 30-69 years. The median age was 48 years with an interquartile range (IQR) of 42-57 years.

In our study shoulder pathologies showed a peak in 45-50 years of life.

Gender Wise Distribution of Shoulder Pathologies: The majority of the study participants were males (31; 59.6%). Rest participants were females (21; 40.4%). A major number of elderly participants were males. Most of the female participants in our study were below 60 years of age. Majority of the male participants were labourers and females were students

Side of Involvement: All the participants had unilateral injuries and suspected tears on single sides only. Twenty-three (44.2%) of them had injury on the left side and rest twenty-nine (55.8%) got injured on their right shoulders. None of the

patients had clinical signs, symptoms, MRI or arthroscopy findings suggestive of bilateral tears.

According to our study the most commonly involved tendon was found to be supraspinatus which included a total of 28 cases (53%). There was an equal incidence of infraspinatus and subscapularis tendon involvement including 11 each (21%). Only a single case of biceps tear was reported. No cases of teres minor tendon involvement was noted in either MRI or arthroscopy making it the least commonly involved tendon amongst the rotator cuff.

Spectrum of Supraspinatus Pathologies: Out of the total 52 cases 28 showed supraspinatus tendon involvement. The most commonly affected pathology of supraspinatus tendon was found to be partial thickness tear which was seen in 19 cases (67.8%) followed by full thickness tear seen in 8 cases (28.5%). Supraspinatus was also the most commonly involved tendon in tendinitis which was seen in 7 out of 8 cases diagnosed with tendinitis on MRI. Two out of three cases of impingement syndrome showed supraspinatus tendon involvement.

Table 3: Spectrum of supraspinatus pathologies

Supraspinatus tendon pathologies	No. of participants
Normal	24
PTT	19
FTT	8
Tendinitis	7
Impingement syndrome	2

Spectrum of infraspinatus pathologies: Out of the total 52 cases 11 had infraspinatus tendon involvement. There was an almost equal incidence of Partial and full thickness tear, 5(45%) and 4(36%). Only one case out of the total 8 cases was found to have infraspinatus tendinitis.

Figure 1: Spectrum of infraspinatus pathologies

Spectrum of Subscapularis Pathologies: Out of the total 52 cases 11 were found to have subscapularis tendon involvement. A total of 7(63%) cases of full thickness tear were diagnosed on MRI making it the most common pathology

followed by partial thickness tear having 4(36%) cases. Out of the 3 cases of impingement syndrome one was shown to have subscapularis tendon involvement.

Table 4: Spectrum of subscapularis pathologies

Subscapularis tendon pathologies	No. of participants
Normal	41
PTT	4
FTT	7
Tendinitis	0
Impingement syndrome	1

Spectrum of Biceps pathologies: Out of the total 52 cases only 1 case showed partial thickness tear of biceps tendon which was confirmed on arthroscopy suggesting that involvement of biceps is common amongst the muscles surrounding shoulder joint.

Figure 2: Spectrum of biceps pathologies

Rotator Cuff Tear Evaluation: All the 52 participants were first assessed first by MRI scan followed by arthroscopy. The MRI scans reported 20 (38.5%) FTT and 29 (55.8%) PTT. On the other hand, arthroscopy revealed 24 (46.2%) FTT and 25 (48.1%) partial thickness tears (PTT). Three (5.8%)

participants did not have any grades of tears as per both the investigations. Forty-four (84.6%) of the 52 participants in our study had the same diagnosis with arthroscopy and MRI. Only 8 (15.4%) participants had different arthroscopy findings than their MRI scans.

Figure 3: Full-thickness (FTT) and partial-thickness tears (PTT) on MRI and Arthroscopy

Osteochondral lesions

Bankart lesion: As per MRI scans and arthroscopy, there were 15 (28.8%) and 18 (34.6%) Bankart lesions, respectively. Further on arthroscopy 3 (5.8%) more cases of Bankart lesions were identified which were missed on MRI in the study participants. Hence in 15 (83.3%) out of 52

participants of our study MRI diagnosis corresponded with the arthroscopy findings.

Hill-Sachs Lesion: As per MRI scans and arthroscopy, there were 14 (26.9%) and 13 (25.0%) Hill-Sachs lesions, respectively. Forty-nine (94.2%) of the 52 participants in our study had their MRI diagnosis matched with arthroscopy findings.

Figure 4: Osteochondral lesions on MRI and Arthroscopy

SLAP tears: As per the MRI scans, there was only one (1.9%) SLAP tear. On contrary, arthroscopy revealed 3 (5.8%) SLAP tears in the study participants. Hence out of 3 cases only 1 case of SLAP tear was picked up by MRI suggesting its poor efficacy in picking up SLAP tear.

Figure 5: SLAP tear on MRI and Arthroscopy

Tendinitis: Out of the total 52 cases 8(15%)cases were diagnosed to have tendinitis on MRI and 11(21%) on arthroscopy. Supraspinatus was the most commonly involved tendon having 7 diagnosed cases on MRI and 9 on arthroscopy.

Table 5: Tendinitis in rotator cuff tendons

TENDINITIS	MRI	ARTHROSCOPY
SUPRASPINATUS	7	9
INFRASPINATUS	1	1
TERES MINOR	0	0
SUBSCAPULARIS	0	1

Joint effusion and Bursitis: Out of all the 52 cases 35(67%) cases showed joint effusion on MRI and 37(71%) showed effusion on arthroscopy making it

the most commonly occurring pathology overall and also the most common associated finding with rotator cuff tear.

Bursitis was seen in 20 out of 52 cases on MRI and 17 on arthroscopy. Sub acromial sub deltooid bursa was the most common one involved.

Table 6: Joint effusion and Bursitis on MRI and Arthroscopy

Pathology	MRI	Arthroscopy
Joint Effusion	35	37
Bursitis	20	17

Impingement syndrome: Out of total 52 cases 3 were diagnosed to have impingement on MRI which was confirmed on arthroscopy.

Figure 6: Impingement syndrome on MRI and Arthroscopy

Table 7: Comparison of MRI and arthroscopy findings in shoulder pathologies

Pathology	Mri Diagnosis	Arthroscopy	DISC
PTT	29	25	5
FTT	20	24	-2
BANKART	15	18	-3
HILLSACH	14	13	1
SLAP	1	3	-2
JE	35	37	-2
BURSITIS	20	17	3
IMPINGEMENT	3	3	0
TENDINITIS	8	11	-3

Table 8: Table showing diagnostic accuracy of MRI in various shoulder

Pathology	T P	T N	F P	F N	Sensitivity	Specificty	PPV	NPV	Diagnostic Accuracy
PTT	25	20	3	2	92.50%	86.90%	89%	90.90%	90%
FTT	20	30	1	1	95.20%	96.70%	95.20%	96.70%	96.10%
BANKART	15	32	2	3	83.30%	94.10%	88.20%	91.40%	90.38%
HILLSACHS	13	38	2	1	93%	95%	87%	97.40%	94%
SLAP	1	49	0	2	33.30%	100%	100.00 %	96.01%	96.10%
JE	35	15	0	2	94.50%	100%	100.00 %	88.20%	96.12%
BURSITIS	20	17	3	0	100%	88.40%	86.90%	100%	94.20%
IMPINGEMENT	3	49	0	0	100%	100%	100%	100.00 %	100%
TENDINITIS	8	42	1	3	80%	100%	88.80%	93.30%	96.15%

Table 9: Table showing P value and correlation coefficient in various shoulder pathologies

Pathology	Correlation coefficient	95% CI	p-value
PTT	0.81	(0.78-0.84)	0.003
FTT	0.86	(0.82-0.90)	0.002
BANKART	0.79	(0.76-0.82)	0.003
HILL SACHS	0.85	(0.81-0.89)	0.003
SLAP	0.86	(0.83-0.89)	0.002
JE	0.91	(0.87-0.95)	< 0.001
BURSITIS	0.87	(0.84-0.91)	0.003
IMPINGEMENT	0.97	(0.96-0.98)	< 0.001
TENDINITIS	0.87	(0.84-0.90)	0.002

Figure 7: Image A, B: Coronal and Sagittal - fat-suppressed proton density sequence demonstrates diffuse PD-FS Hyper intensity involving the myotendinous junction of supraspinatus muscle suggestive of full thickness tear. Image C and D: Pre and post-operative images showing full thickness tear of supraspinatus and its repair.

Figure 8: Image A, B and C: Sagittal T2, Sagittal and Axial - fat-suppressed proton density sequence demonstrating diffuse PD-FS Hyper intensity involving the subscapularis muscle suggestive of full thickness tear. Image D: Arthroscopic image of a subscapularis tear.

Discussions

The role of MRI in the evaluation of shoulder pain and its correlation with Arthroscopy has been extensively studied in the literature [14,15]. The provided table presents valuable insights into the diagnostic performance of MRI across various shoulder pathologies, including rotator cuff tears, Bankart's tears, SLAP lesions and others.

In our study in the rotator cuff tears, the sensitivity and specificity of MRI reported align well with previous literature, [16,17] indicating its reliability in detecting these common shoulder injuries. This consistency reinforces MRI's established role as a primary imaging modality for diagnosing rotator cuff tears, allowing for accurate preoperative planning and better patient outcomes. Similarly, for Bankart's tears and Hill-Sachs lesions, MRI demonstrates high sensitivity and specificity, corroborating previous findings. These results emphasize the utility of MRI in identifying shoulder instability and associated structural abnormalities, guiding surgical decision-making, and predicting postoperative outcomes.

However, the lower sensitivity and high specificity observed for SLAP lesions in the present series could be attributed to less number of study participants and lack of administration of contrast in joint cavity. Previous literature [18,19,20] also suggests that SLAP lesions can be challenging to diagnose accurately with MRI alone due to their

subtle presentation and variable imaging features. Therefore, clinicians need to interpret MRI findings cautiously in suspected SLAP lesions and consider supplementary diagnostic modalities, such as arthroscopy, for definitive diagnosis and treatment planning. In cases of tendinitis MRI was found to have a good accuracy in comparison to previous studies in literature. However, a higher incidence of false positivity and negativity in studies, can be attributed to the limitation of MRI in distinguishing between a partial thickness tear and tendinitis. High resolution imaging in 3T MRI would have delineated the pathology better.

The excellent diagnostic accuracy of MRI for other pathologies such as joint effusion (JE), bursitis, impingement, and tendinitis highlights its overall effectiveness in evaluating shoulder pain. These findings are consistent with existing evidence supporting MRI as a valuable tool for comprehensive shoulder assessment, facilitating targeted interventions and improved patient care.

Despite the strengths of MRI, it is essential to acknowledge its limitations, including cost, availability, and potential over diagnosis of clinically insignificant findings. Additionally, while MRI provides detailed anatomical information, its ability to assess functional aspects of shoulder pathology remains limited. Therefore, integrating clinical assessment, patient history, and imaging findings is crucial for accurate diagnosis and optimal management of shoulder pain.

Limitations

1. The sample size in our study is limited, potentially affecting the generalizability of the findings. A larger sample size would have enhanced the robustness of the results and allow for subgroup analyses.
2. The use of Arthroscopy as the reference standard for diagnosing shoulder pathologies may introduce bias, as it is an invasive procedure and subject to interpretation variability among surgeons.
3. The interpretation of MRI findings may vary among Radiologists, potentially influencing the accuracy of diagnosis.
4. Lack of availability of a 3T MRI which provides higher signal-to-noise ratio and spatial resolution, which can potentially improve the visualization of small anatomical structures and subtle pathology in the shoulder.

Summary

1. Supraspinatus is the most commonly affected tendon followed by infraspinatus and subscapularis tendon with partial thickness tear of supraspinatus being the most common pathology.
2. MRI demonstrated outstanding diagnostic accuracy in evaluation of partial and full thickness rotator cuff tear in correlation with arthroscopy.
3. Although MRI showed a reliable diagnostic accuracy in evaluation of tendinitis, yet few mimic PTT, suggesting limited role of MRI in differentiating the two entities which are to be confirmed on arthroscopy.
4. MRI demonstrated high diagnostic accuracy in evaluation of Bankart and Hillsach's lesion in correlation to arthroscopy. MRI should be used wherever conservative management is planned and MRI cannot be replaced by arthroscopy as arthroscopy is preferred whenever MRI is contraindicated and surgery has to be done.
5. MRI showed low sensitivity and high false negativity suggesting its limited role in evaluation of SLAP tear in correlation to arthroscopy.
6. MRI showed excellent diagnostic accuracy in evaluation of impingement syndrome, joint effusion and bursitis in correlation with arthroscopy.

Conclusions

The present study concluded that the MRI serves as a valuable non-invasive tool for guiding clinical decision-making and optimizing outcomes in patients of shoulder pain.

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